

VIEWS OF WESTERN SCIENTISTS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY. PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE POST-SOVIET REGIME.

Setsalieva Ilmira Ismoilovna

Kokan State Pedagogical Institute Head of the Department of Preschool Education.

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Abstract. *In the development of psychology, the views of Western scientists Lev Semenovich Vygotsky, Sergei Leonidovich Rubinstein, Alexey Nikolaevich Leontiev, Lomov Boris Fedorovich, Alexander Grigorievich Asmolov are discussed separately. Psychological development in the post-Soviet period is revealed.*

Keywords: *Society, development, activity, intellectual intellect, philosophical worldview, historical period, factor, personality, young age, worldview.*

ВЗГЛЯДЫ ЗАПАДНЫХ УЧЕНЫХ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИИ. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ В ПОСТСОВЕТСКИЙ РЕЖИМ.

Аннотация. *В развитии психологии отдельно рассматриваются взгляды западных ученых Льва Семеновича Выготского, Сергея Леонидовича Рубинштейна, Алексея Николаевича Леонтьева, Ломова Бориса Федоровича, Александра Григорьевича Асмолова. Раскрывается психологическое развитие в постсоветский период.*

Ключевые слова: *Общество, развитие, деятельность, интеллектуальный интеллект, философское мировоззрение, исторический период, фактор, личность, молодой возраст, мировоззрение.*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the development of society, people's life activity expands, their intellectual intellect is enriched. Consequently, their philosophical worldview also becomes an important factor in the development of society as a reflection of the historical period. For this reason, different periods of human development lead to the emergence of different forms of philosophy.

Each person is the owner of certain social relations characteristic of his age, and is the object of many economic, political, legal and moral influences exerted on him by society. The character, temperament, and abilities of a person are manifested in work and life when he experiences mental processes. Therefore, the interrelation and connection of mental processes, mental states and mental characteristics constitute the psychological structure of a person.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Lev Semenovich Vygotsky (1896-1934) - put forward the concept of cultural-historical development. Paying special attention to reactions, he believed that the most important is the reaction of speech in humans. Speech is a bodily movement, but unlike other bodily movements,

it emphasizes that it gives new dimensions to human consciousness. Firstly, speech occurs in the process of communication, so it is essentially social. Secondly, it always has a mental aspect, which is the meaning of the word. Thirdly, a word can exist independently of an object as an element of culture.

Thus, the speech reaction embodies the bodily, social (communicative), spiritual and historical-cultural. In these 4 coordinate systems (individuality, behavior, meaning, culture), Vygotsky tries to explain any phenomenon of human mental life. A symbol (word) is a "psychological weapon" with the help of which consciousness is built. Its peculiarity is that it requires processing with working tools. They change both the external nature and the person. Vygotsky experimentally proved that egocentric speech in children does not originate from the child's inclinations and fantasy that are far from reality. He is the organizer of practical actions.

Thinking to himself, the child plans an action. In "Thinking and Speech" (1934), Vygotsky studied the development of concepts in children based on experimental research. According to Vygotsky, only education that precedes development gives good results. The term "coastal development zone" is introduced. This concept implies a gap between the levels of tasks that a child can solve independently under the guidance of adults. Learning creates such a zone and leads to development.

Sergei Leonidovich Rubinstein put forward the principle of the unity of consciousness and activity in his work "Fundamentals of General Psychology". Combining consciousness with the process of activity, Rubinstein explained how it is formed in this process. This specific study radically changed the worldview. A person's contact with the world is not direct and indirect, but his real actions with the objects of this world.

The idea that it is carried out through a medium changed the views on consciousness. Its dependence on objective actions, and not on external objects, has become one of the important problems of psychology. Consciousness sets goals, organizes the subject's activity and reflects reality in emotional and mental images. It is assumed that the nature of consciousness was initially dictated by social, public relations. Since these relations change from period to period, consciousness is a historically changeable product. The idea that everything is realized in the human psyche in his activity.

Also developed by Alexei Nikolaevich Leontiev (1903-1979). At first, he follows Vygotsky's path. Later, he highly appreciates Basvo's ideas about the morphology of activity. He offers his own scheme for organizing activity and changing levels: that is, this process occurs in the evolution of the animal world, the history of human society, and also in the individual development of man. ("Problem Psychology of Development", 1959).

According to Leontiev, activity is a separate entity. It includes structural components: activity, actions, operations, psychophysiological functions. The components of the activity structure correspond to the components of the motivational field: motive, goal, conditions, as well as the components of consciousness - meaning, significance, "emotional texture". They cannot be separated.

Boris Fedorovich Lomov (1927-1989) - a specialist in the field of general, engineering, cognitive psychology, educational psychology, behavioral psychology, Doctor of Psychology, professor. In 1972-1989, he worked as the director of the Institute of Psychology, founder and editor-in-chief of the "Psychological Journal". Together with B.G. Ananov, he opens the psychology department of Leningrad University and holds the position of dean for several years.

Most of his work is aimed at studying general psychological problems. He puts forward many ideas on behavioral psychology ("Communication and Cognition", 1984). Lomov is one of the founders of engineering psychology. He pays special attention to the methodological and theoretical problems of psychology, including analyzing the categorical apparatus of psychology, revealing the internal unity and structural system of psychological knowledge, its conditions and development trends, determining the ways of constructing psychological theories, exploring the relationship between theory, experiment and practice in psychology, etc.

Alexander Grigorievich Asmolov (1949) is a specialist in the field of methodology and theory of psychology. A student of A.N. Leontiev and A.R. Luria. His scientific and organizational work was aimed not only at introducing pedagogical ideas into the field of education, but also at training practicing psychologists and organizing psychological services.

1. The position and trends of psychology

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, psychology became the most scientific and experimental direction.

CONCLUSION

During the Soviet regime, psychology was tied to the socio-political context and ideological interests, but after independence, the important influence of development based on global standards, modern scientific principles and free research became evident in the rise of the field of psychology from one direction to another. The development of psychology in the post-Soviet period has led to a number of important changes, updates, and the emergence of new directions. While in the Soviet era, psychology was often based on ideological interests, Marxist-Leninist philosophy and was strictly controlled by the state, in the post-independence period, the field has undergone many new scientific directions, free research and global standards of scientific research.

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